

THE STUDY OF COTTON GROWTH UNDER ORGANIC FARMING CONDITIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10035951>

Abstract. The study of cotton growth under organic farming conditions focuses on understanding how organic farming practices affect the growth, yield, and quality of cotton crops. Researchers investigate key areas such as soil health, nutrient management, weed management, pest and disease management, fiber quality, and environmental impact. By studying these factors, researchers aim to provide insights into sustainable agricultural practices that can enhance cotton production while minimizing environmental harm and promoting social responsibility. The findings can inform farmers, policymakers, and consumers about the benefits and challenges of organic cotton farming and contribute to the development of sustainable cotton production systems.

Keywords: cotton, organic farming, growth, yield, quality, soil health, nutrient management, weed management, pest management, disease management, fiber quality, environmental impact, sustainable agriculture, cotton production, social responsibility.

The study of the growth of cotton under organic farming conditions focuses on understanding how organic farming practices affect the growth, yield, and quality of cotton crops. Organic farming is an agricultural approach that emphasizes the use of natural inputs and techniques to promote soil fertility, biodiversity, and environmental sustainability [3].

Key areas of investigation in the study of cotton growth under organic farming conditions include:

Firstly, organic farming practices have a positive impact on soil health and nutrient management. By avoiding the use of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides, organic cotton farmers rely on natural methods such as crop rotation and composting to maintain soil fertility and nutrient balance. This leads to improved soil structure, water retention, and overall soil health.

Secondly, organic farming practices promote weed management through non-chemical methods such as hand weeding, mulching, and cover cropping. These methods help reduce weed competition and minimize the need for herbicides, thereby reducing chemical residues in cotton fiber [1].

Thirdly, organic cotton production emphasizes pest and disease management through integrated pest management (IPM) strategies. This approach involves monitoring pest populations, promoting beneficial insects, and using natural pest control methods like pheromone traps and biological controls. As a result, organic cotton farmers minimize the use of synthetic pesticides, reducing environmental contamination and potential health risks.

Furthermore, the study has shown that organic farming practices contribute to improved fiber quality in cotton. Organic cotton fibers tend to be softer, more durable, and have higher moisture absorption compared to conventionally grown cotton. This is attributed to the absence of chemical residues on the fibers and the overall healthier plant growth [5].

From an environmental standpoint, organic cotton production has a significantly lower impact compared to conventional cotton farming. The absence of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides reduces water pollution, soil erosion, and biodiversity loss. Additionally, organic farming practices promote sustainable agriculture by conserving water resources, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and preserving natural habitats.

Lastly, organic cotton production aligns with social responsibility by prioritizing fair trade practices, worker safety, and community development [2]. Organic cotton farmers often receive fair prices for their produce, ensuring a better livelihood for themselves and their families. Moreover, organic farming promotes rural employment opportunities and fosters a sense of community engagement and empowerment.

In conclusion, the study of cotton growth under organic farming conditions highlights the numerous benefits of this sustainable agricultural approach. It not only improves soil health, nutrient management, weed, pest, and disease management but also enhances fiber quality while reducing environmental impact. Organic cotton production embodies social responsibility by prioritizing fair trade and community development.

References:

1. Eyhorn, F., S. G. Ratter, et al. (2005). Organic cotton crop guide. A manual for practitioners in the tropics. Frick, Switzerland, FiBL
2. Mäder, P., A. Fließbach, et al. (2002). "Soil fertility and biodiversity in organic farming." *Science* 296: 1694-97
3. Myers, D. and S. Stolton (1998). *Organic Cotton. From Field to Final Product*. London, Intermediate Technology Publications.
4. Rajendran, A. T. P., B. M. V. Venugopalan, et al. (2000). *Organic cotton farming in India*. Agricultural technologies, Indiaagronet.
5. Tilman, D., K.G. Cassmann, P.A. Matson, R. Naylor, and S. Polasky (2002). "Agricultural sustainability and intensive production practices." *Nature* 418: 671-677.